

Designing Learning pathways

We would like you to collect some information about your experiences in the context of HPC Education and training. Please share your thoughts on the exercise and the design process in general.

This survey is meant to be fully anonymous and we will share responses with the community. Please don't include identifying information in your responses to the free-text questions

We hope to use the information to guide the creation of best practices for designing learning pathways for our community.

How would you describe your role in the educational context?

Was this your first attempt at designing a learning pathway?

Take a moment and reflect on the following:

Where did you start your design process?

Is the pathway you designed (or envisioned) linear?

What was the most challenging part in designing a learning pathway?

Choosing what start point to use

Connecting the dots and filling in the gaps

Only picking the most relevant points

Making it general

Remembering the past courses and their order

Choosing how to prioritise one skill over another

Choosing a role/ purpose of the pathway

Finding a starting point applicable to others

What was the most challenging part in designing a learning pathway?

Keeping the path interesting and, at the same time, goal oriented.

Understand the final objective

Too choose from the skills set!

Finding an order between the different skills

Connecting the dots and tracing the path back

Putting Skills in the most meaningful/practical order

Identify subjects of the pathway

Trying to think of reasonable start/end points

What was the most challenging part in designing a learning pathway?

Grasping the scope of the possibilities

Thinking about the interdependencies

Deciding what was universal enough to be included for the starting point + ending point persona

Knowing the dependencies and capacity for parallel skill acquisition.

Deciding which level of knowledge of a certain skill is sufficient (to move on)

Some skills were not available

Finding useful blobs to describe learning points ...

Finding the right entry point
Finding good sequences, need to alternate between high level concepts

What was the most challenging part in designing a learning pathway?

Figuring out the relevant training items at the right time to not cause them to be detracted from their research work.

Doing it in 20 minutes!

Still being in the middle of the pathway

Aligning with a specific example for a role type - there are many options to change track

Suppose I looked at it from a number of roles we needed to develop, not just RSE. Difficultly picking out key areas for focus of role I chose

Identifying knowledge and experience picked up on the way

Where to start and where to finish which is never ending

1. People, the work and tech evolve and change. Best to establish several foundations and facilitate ease of ongoing access
2. People are in teams

What was the most challenging part in designing a learning pathway?

A huge number of skills are required, I could have almost circled most of the "software development" section before beginning

Recalling my own early career and what was most influential

Start to end pathways

What challenges do you think people may encounter following the pathway you designed?

Understanding it

Work pressures get in the way

Sticking to it

Finding the ways to train for these skills and having certification to prove the skill

None (if they want to learn)

It takes too long, but generates a generalist

Lacking skills they need in their work right now, but come later.

Keeping pace, and integrating it in a timeline with their work

What challenges do you think people may encounter following the pathway you designed?

Takes a long time to learn/acquire skills

Pressure to deliver on their project

It may not fit to the individual needs

Getting frustrated about the diversity of topics and how big the individual topics are

Missing prerequisite knowledge

Start point has a lot of background already

Resources, use cases, employer support...

A lot of modules in the pathway - time, examples, resources - to accomplish this

What challenges do you think people may encounter following the pathway you designed?

It is too personal and depends on my particular field of research

time to reach the goal

They might start at a different point

Time/grant restraints.
Needing to just get results.
Inherited code that does not follow good design

Finding mentorship and support

Having the time to do it.

Hpc knowledge not relevant for some research fields

Finding the right way to learn and consolidate the skill before moving to the next step

What challenges do you think people may encounter following the pathway you designed?

Irrelevance? The pathway was needs-driven and the exact order/details may be unique

To create concrete path for learning

Learning outside of a real world work project

Difficult to do off-the-job

Timetraveling ... started somewhere in 19XX ... ended somewhere else in 202X 😊

Paths of role models

Recommendations and guidance from others

What can be done to make learning pathways easier to discover and navigate?

Problem to skill map

I do not know...

Make contact with domain scientist early on.

Searchable / browsable by similar starting / end points

Provide a repository of pathways.

More awareness and a centralized platform that consolidates all these training requirements and learning pathways

Pre canned ones as you are trying to do and signposting to relevant resources

Make them dynamic and interactive

What can be done to make learning pathways easier to discover and navigate?

Collate some of these ones

Using AI tools

Collect them and make students aware that it exists

Need to align for specific career options

Websites that centrally list different courses and materials

Make higher level example pathways where people can add their own specifics

Advertise it

Have clear and understandable skill names/descriptions, which highlight dependencies, leading to natural pathways

What can be done to make learning pathways easier to discover and navigate?

What can be done to create a(n objectively) greatest painting? 🤖

provide pre-defined routes, with the possibility to "jump" between

And the Time Machine mentioned before.....

Communication with relevant stakeholders

Precise documentation

Add required knowledge to skills

Outreach

There is no free lunch

What can be done to make learning pathways easier to discover and navigate?

Having a PI pushing you to educate yourself.

Standardized/accepted certifications at the end of the path

Peer mentorships/apprenticeships, senior colleagues taking an active role in developing new talent

Mentoring?

Having an online resource with courses, events, training materials... all in one place that is promoted

Ability to customise / choose from different "implementation" options / focuses for reach skill

Having smart connected people able to teach

Make them accessible to the public in suitable forums and allowing individuals to copy and tune them

What can be done to make learning pathways easier to discover and navigate?

Have example pathways based on commonly chosen paths

Please provide any other thoughts or comments that would help with creating guidance for pathway design:

We need advisors in the field

After foundational, address in a teams context

Having more options (especially around evolving technologies)

Make the skill tree a map with requirements and highlighting pathways in 3D space

Collect stories about paths that have been taken.

Definition of the modules . Sometimes words mean different things

Making short term pathways might be good - e.g. next 3 months. Then do it again.

Gather more and more feedback from professionals, educators and students

Please provide any other thoughts or comments that would help with creating guidance for pathway design:

Start specific with real examples from people in the role then look for commonalities / abstractions / choices among those

options for different learners persona

The logic behind the order needs to be explained thoroughly.

Creating a story based approach? I.e. asking users a series of questions for which a binary response is expected, and creating a custom pathway for each individual user.

Making a better definition of the "starting point"

Not everyone needs all skills, design bird eye skills

Domain scientists often need to know why software practices are important, as it may not be obvious to them why it is needed

Enable adjacent access, ie from the side, other fields

Please provide any other thoughts or comments that would help with creating guidance for pathway design:

Aggressive gathering of mid/ exit interviews of learners

Pathways imply an order, would be better to indicate specific skill sets and the depth of knowledge required. See SOFIA for general IT space

Have yoe seen this list
<https://de-rse.org/learn-and-teach/learn/>

Interesting

Too short

An endpoint feels final, pathways could have milestones instead as our field is always changing, so should the pathways

☁️ What word would you use to describe this session?

54 responses

Thanks for the *your* feedback

We will share the responses with the community!